

Nematode resistance of IRRI breeding lines in Assam, India

N.K. Sarma, D. Das, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS); S.A. Hussain, Haji Abdul Majid Memorial Hospital and Research Center; B. Barman, District Agricultural Office, Assam, India; and D. Senadhira*, IRRI

The deepwater rice area in eastern India is about 10% of wet-season rice. During the last 20 yr, deepwater rice farmers in the area have experienced increased incidence of ufra disease, caused by the rice stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*. The nematode perpetuates in floodwater and has spread rapidly—sometimes leaving no panicle to harvest. Several phytosanitary measures such as stubble burning, deep plowing, alternate field drying, delayed sowing, crop rotation, and chemical application have been recommended. These

methods have not been fully adopted, however, because of water problems and socioeconomic reasons. Under such situations, water control and use of resistant varieties appear efficient.

We evaluated 19 advanced *D. angustus*-resistant breeding lines of IRRI-Bangladesh origin for their reaction to *D. angustus*, plant height, and yield in North Lakhimpur during 1995-97 (Tables 1 and 2). Agronomic evaluation for plant height and grain yield per hectare was done in a *D. angustus*-free area in 10 × 2-m plots

with 25 × 25-cm spacing. Ufra incidence was tested in a high-disease-pressure area with additional inoculum 1 mo after transplanting. Laboratory tests were conducted to determine nematode population in the first internode of the stem as well as in the whole plant to confirm the presence of *D. angustus*. Ufra incidence was calculated from the ratio of number of panicles infested to total number of panicles, expressed in percentage. The percentage value was transformed to an arc sine value for statistical analysis.

Table 1. Incidence of ufra in panicles of *D. angustus*-resistant breeding lines, Assam, 1995-97.

Line	Panicles affected by ufra ^a (%)						
	1995		1996		1997		Av
IR63142-J6-B-1-1	5.3	(13.3)	6.2	(14.4)	7.5	(15.9)	6.3
IR63142-J8-B-2-1	4.6	(12.4)	4.4	(12.1)	3.6	(10.9)	4.2
IR63142-J8-B-2-2	7.7	(16.1)	6.0	(14.2)	5.7	(13.8)	6.5
IR63153-J9-B-1-1	6.3	(14.5)	5.6	(13.7)	7.3	(15.7)	6.4
IR63188-J8-B-1-1	9.2	(17.7)	7.2	(15.6)	11.2	(19.6)	9.2
IR63188-J8-B-7-1	7.4	(15.8)	6.2	(14.4)	10.1	(18.5)	7.9
IR63188-J8-B-7-2	6.6	(14.9)	5.8	(13.9)	9.6	(18.0)	7.3
IR63225-J2-B-1-1	5.2	(13.2)	5.8	(13.9)	6.7	(15.0)	5.9
IR63225-J2-B-4-1	4.1	(11.7)	4.8	(12.7)	8.3	(16.7)	5.7
IR63225-J2-B-4-2	9.5	(18.0)	5.2	(13.2)	10.5	(18.9)	8.4
IR63225-J2-B-6-1	10.1	(18.5)	9.6	(18.0)	10.1	(18.5)	9.9
IR63225-J2-B-6-2	7.2	(15.6)	6.2	(14.4)	6.6	(14.9)	6.7
IR63645-J3-B-9-1	5.5	(13.6)	4.6	(12.4)	11.3	(19.6)	7.1
IR63174-J1-B-3-1	11.5	(19.8)	9.2	(17.7)	12.1	(20.4)	10.9
IR63174-J1-B-3-2	12.3	(20.5)	8.6	(17.0)	15.4	(23.1)	12.1
IR63174-J1-B-2-3	14.2	(22.1)	10.2	(18.6)	13.2	(21.3)	12.5
IR63174-J1-B-4-3	7.5	(15.9)	6.6	(14.9)	5.4	(13.4)	6.5
IR63174-J1-B-6-3	10.2	(18.6)	8.2	(16.6)	13.2	(21.3)	10.5
IR63174-J3-B-1-2	8.5	(17.0)	7.6	(16.0)	11.5	(19.8)	9.2
Rangabao (susceptible check)	80.3	(63.6)	81.8	(64.8)	79.7	(63.2)	80.6
Rayada B3 (resistant check)	26.3	(30.8)	15.2	(23.0)	14.5	(22.4)	18.7
Mean	(19.2)		(17.7)		(20.0)		
Intervarietal differences	HS ^b		HS		HS		
LSD(0.05)	(7.09)		(7.13)		(6.69)		

^aArc sine-transformed value in parentheses. ^bHS = highly significant.

*Deceased

Table 2. Plant height and grain yield of *D. angustus*-resistant breeding lines, Assam, 1995-97.

Line	Plant height (cm)				Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			
	1995	1996	1997	Av	1995	1996	1997	Av
IR63142-J6-B-1-1	160	174	162	165.3	1.1	2.1	1.0	1.4
IR63142-J8-B-2-1	159	185	169	171.0	1.3	2.2	1.0	1.5
IR63142-J8-B-2-2	163	186	162	170.3	1.6	2.0	1.0	1.5
IR63153-J9-B-1-1	179	194	182	185.0	3.3	2.4	2.0	2.6
IR63188-J8-B-1-1	161	167	169	165.7	0.9	0.9	1.1	1.0
IR63188-J8-B-7-1	130	149	162	147.0	0.8	1.1	1.0	1.0
IR63188-J8-B-7-2	128	135	141	134.7	0.9	1.4	2.0	1.4
IR63225-J2-B-1-1	146	154	146	148.7	1.0	1.7	1.1	1.3
IR63225-J2-B-4-1	133	141	139	137.7	0.3	1.0	0.9	0.7
IR63225-J2-B-4-2	152	160	152	154.7	0.6	1.3	0.9	0.9
IR63225-J2-B-6-1	166	179	156	167.0	1.3	1.7	1.4	1.5
IR63225-J2-B-6-2	167	176	174	172.3	2.4	2.2	1.4	2.0
IR63645-J3-B-9-1	143	151	145	146.3	1.0	1.7	1.1	1.3
IR63174-J1-B-3-1	97	103	103	101.0	3.1	4.3	1.6	3.0
IR63174-J1-B-3-2	101	106	108	105.0	3.3	4.4	1.8	3.2
IR63174-J1-B-2-3	105	112	107	108.0	2.8	4.2	1.9	3.0
IR63174-J1-B-4-3	117	116	150	127.7	0.7	1.4	1.2	1.1
IR63174-J1-B-6-3	101	112	114	109.0	3.1	3.0	2.0	2.7
IR63174-J3-B-1-2	91	87	92	90.0	2.4	3.1	2.4	2.6
Rangabao (susceptible check)	161	155	182	166.0	1.8	1.3	2.2	1.8
Rayada B3 (resistant check)	140	151	160	150.3	2.2	3.7	2.8	2.8
Mean	138.1	147.3	146.4		1.71	2.25	1.52	
Intervarietal differences	HS ^a	HS	HS		HS	HS	HS	
LSD 0.05	17.4	20.0	17.3		0.64	0.72	0.35	

^aHS = Highly significant.

Highly significant differences in ufra incidence in panicles were observed among all varieties including the checks (Table 1). Ufra-infested panicles ranged from 3.6% for IR63142-J8-B-2-1 in 1997 to 81.8% for Rangabao in 1996. Advanced lines were resistant in all 3 yr and performed better than resistant check Rayada B3.

Entries IR63174-J1-B-3-2 and IR63174-J1-B-3-1 had an average yield of more than 3 t ha⁻¹ during 1995-97 (Table 2). Considering their height, Rayada B3, IR63153-J9-B-1-1, and IR63225-J2-B-6-2 may be more suitable for deeply flooded areas of Assam because of their lower rate of *D. angustus* infestation and high productivity. The other lines, which are shorter (90-109 cm), may be suitable for less flooded areas.

Rayada B3, IR63153-J9-B-1-1, and IR63225-J2-B-6-2 are more suitable for the deeply flooded areas of Assam because of the lower rate of D. angustus infestation and higher productivity.

Identification of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* by insertion sequence-based polymerase chain reaction (IS-PCR)

T. Adhikari, Rice Program, Agrium Biologicals, 402-15 Innovation Place, Saskatoon, SK S7N 2X8, Canada; C.M. Vera Cruz, and T.W. Mew, IRRI; and J.E. Leach, Kansas State University, USA

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) methods based on repetitive element sequences such as BOX, ERIC, and REP (collectively called rep-PCR) are useful in identifying many phytopathogenic bacteria. Because these sequences are common to most gram-negative bacteria, they will amplify DNA from most genera of bacteria. While these techniques are excellent for comparing bacteria at the species and genus levels, their lack of specificity limits their application in answering certain questions at the subspecies and population levels. In practical diagnosis, the ability to rapidly differentiate *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv.

oryzae (*Xoo*)—the cause of bacterial blight of rice—from other pathovars of *Xanthomonas* including *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzicola*—(*Xocola*)—the bacterial leaf streak pathogen of rice—is necessary, but often techniques for differentiation are not readily available.

In this study, we explored the use of primers whose sequences are based on two high-copy insertion elements, *IS1112* and *IS1113*, isolated previously from *Xoo*. Because the elements are in high copy and dispersed differently in the genome, we reasoned that outwardly directed primers from each (Fig. 1) would amplify intergenic

regions that would exhibit some specificity. Our objective was to develop a sensitive and rapid PCR-based assay to identify and detect *Xoo* in rice.

Based on *IS1112* and *IS1113* sequences, outwardly directed oligonucleotide primers (20 bases long) were designed and synthesized. These primers included N1 (5'-CATCCATCACTGGAACCGG-3') and N2 (5'-CCTGACGTCAGTTCGTCCAG-3') from *IS1112* and J1 (5'-CGAGTCCAGTCCAGCGGACC-3') from *IS1113*. DNA from *Escherichia coli*, *Ralstonia solanacearum*, *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *syringae*; 45 strains representing 24 pathovars; and three species of